

PAPER A: RESEARCH ARTICLE

Anaerobic Co-digestion of Fruit Wastes and Lignocellulosic Waste with Cow Dung to Produce Biogas

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Abstract

This work focuses on separate production of biogas from anaerobic co-digestion of fruit wastes including tomato, banana, papaya, peel mango and avocado mixed with cow dung and lignocellulosic waste (LW) plus cow dung, as an alternative power generation source. The work seeks to determine the mixture conditions that could give high yield of biogas. Furthermore, to investigate the effect of total solids (TS)/volatile solids (VS) ratio on biogas production by carrying out physio-chemical analysis for the separate production kept in digester A and B respectively. The anaerobic digestion of mixed fruit wastes required 21 days to completely decompose before producing biogas. Co-digestion between fruits and cow dung provides biogas without the requirement for fertilizer or chemical input to the system after adjusting the elements, such as pH that are influential to anaerobic digestion. Resulting gas produced was tested for combustibility using a Bunsen burner. In order to stop ecological calamities like environmental pollution, deforestation, desertification, and erosion, the hunt for alternate sources of energy like biogas has to be accelerated.

External Link:

Keywords: Fruit waste, Biogas production, Co-digestion, Lignocellulosic waste, Cow dung, Waste management

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1.0. | Introduction

The pace of energy consumption is increasing at unforeseen rates with each day that goes by in a rapidly expanding world. The greatest way to meet any nation's energy needs is through the development of sustainable and renewable energy sources (Bharathiraja et al., 2018; Ngoc et al., 2014). Renewable energy production from locally and easily accessible materials is undoubtedly beneficial and lowers the cost of its production. Environmentally conscious people may decide to compost their fruit waste, lignocellulosic wastes (LW) and cow dung in order to create a beneficial fertilizer or soil amendment, but this method does not provide a way to extract the energy that is trapped in trash. Many municipal waste management initiatives do try to capture the energy contained in organic waste through burning, in waste-to-energy facilities and methane (CH₄) capture from microbial activity in landfills. Even while these systems utilize the energy contained in LW, they do not immediately benefit the people who generate the garbage and may potentially result in increased expenses for them due to collecting (Granado et al., 2017; Nasir et al., 2012).

Breakdown of animal and plant wastes can result in the production of biogas, a kind of renewable energy that is made up mostly of CH₄, carbon dioxide, and trace amounts of nitrogen and hydrogen sulfide (Otero & Mor, 2008). The amount and kind of material introduced to the system determines how much CH₄ is produced during the anaerobic digestion of biologically degradable organic materials. Therefore, there are several techniques to expose leftover food, fruit and vegetable wastes, and cow dung to anaerobic digestion for the purpose of producing energy. Single-phase digestion, two-phase digestion, dry fermentation, and co-digestion are now the most popular ideas (Banks et al., 2011). Co-digestion, which uses a co-substrate to improve biogas yields due to positive synergy created in the digestion medium and the delivery of lacking nutrients for microorganisms, is an intriguing approach for increasing anaerobic digestion of wastes yields (Kuo & Dow, 2017). Therefore, one alternate method for enhancing biogas technology is to anaerobically co-digest, fruit and lignocellulosic waste, to reduce heating expenses. Reactor employed in this kind of system would almost probably need to be run at mesophilic temperatures (between 25°C and 40°C) (Abubakar, et al., 2022). Even if the CH₄ production was higher at thermophilic temperatures (between 55 and 60°C), it most certainly wouldn't be sufficient to justify the expense of keeping the reactors between 15 and 30°C hotter.

Goal of this project is to develop an anaerobic co-digestion system for producing biogas from biologically degradable wastes. Although, anaerobic co-digestion of fruit waste, and LW and cow dung has not yet been used on a large scale to produce biogas, there is a dearth of easily accessible scientific data on the quality of raw biogas and possible emissions during its utilization for power generation. The data is required to choose power-generating machinery, determine the raw biogas conditioning needs for beneficial usage, and get air quality permits. Hence, the overall goal of this study is to develop scientific knowledge regarding the quality and quantity of biogas produced by the anaerobic co-digestion of fruit waste, LW and cow dung, which could also inform one of the mixtures that will give high yield of biogas when placed at two different sealed drums. Furthermore, this work will find the conditions necessary for biogas production so as to generate a scientific assay on conditions that will result in high yield of the gas and its effect on the environment.

2.1. | Resource Gathering

2.1.1. | Biodigester

In this paper, several forms of fruit waste, LW and cow dung were collected in different location in Katsina State in a two different 220-liters sealed cylindrical plastic anaerobic digesters as shown in Fig. 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Drum A: Lignocellulosic Waste Mixed with Cow Dung

Figure 2: Drum B: Fruit waste Mixed with Cow Manure

Cow dung serves as an inoculum for the conversion of the biodegradable waste to biogas. LW and cow dung were mixed in proportion of 50:50 in Drum A, in the same manner fruits waste and cow manure were mixed. In both digesters or drum, equal measurements and feed time as well as equal retention period were allowed to enable the microorganisms inside the cow dung to feed on the wastes, so as to generate biogas product. Exactly, 15-liters of water was fed to the 2 plastic cylindrical drums.

2.1.2. | *Digester Construction and Setup*

Construction of an anaerobic digester for the semi-continuous system shown in Fig. 1 and 2 was first carried out. It is important to describe the two digesters. The container's mouth cover has a 420 mm diameter, drum top and bottom are 360 mm in diameter and 9000 mm high. It also has 3 holes with diameter of 37.5 mm. One of these openings is on the digester's tightly sealed cover and connected to a bucket holding the slurry. It serves as the feed's inlet. The other opening was made at the bottom of the container and served as the digested waste's outlet. Biogas is normally released through the third hole, which had a 12.5 mm diameter and was attached to a gas burner. In order to stop biogas from escaping into the surrounding air, the feed inlet and digested waste outlet were placed below the biogas outlet opening and a pump put in the middle of the cylindrical drum.

2.1.3. | *Substrates Collection*

Mixture of fruit wastes were gathered from Zango, in Daura Local Government, Nigeria, as majority of the dwellers there hawk these fruits while others have stores filled with it for sale. Thus, only a portion of the wastes were hand-picked, taking great care not to allow impurities like stones, tiny polyethene and excessive sand as shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Mixture of Fruit Wastes

This was done also by contacting Tashan Yammaha market of Daura Local Government for fruit leftovers to supplement shortages. Different species of LW shown in Fig. 4 were gathered from the Daura Wood Market due to its abundance and combined for use in this work.

Figure 4: Lignocellulosic Waste Gathered

While cow dung utilized in the study was collected from Mai adu Cattle Market in Katsina State. The gathered cow excrement (Fig. 5) was no older than a day so as to obtain a sample containing microorganisms still at their agile state.

Figure 5: Cow Dung Before and After Mixing with Water

After collecting all the biodegradable organic waste mentioned, they were manually chopped to a size of 1-4 mm to prepare them as feedstock. Table 1 depicts waste collected for the production.

Table 1: Composition of Biomass Used

Waste	Weight (%)
Cow dung	20
Orange peels	8.4
Banana peels	7.2
Avocado	4.5
Papaya	6.3
Mango	10.3
Tomato	3.1
Lignocellulosic waste	40.2

Properties of the wastes some of which are presented by Abubakar & Yunus (2021) were further examined.

2.2. | Mixing and Laboratory Analysis

2.2.1. | Slurry Formulation

A slurry of around 5 kg of mixed waste, which contained 50 LW, 50% cow dung for digester A, and 50% fruits mixed with cow manure, was put into Fig. 1 along with approximately 20 liters of tap water.

2.2.2. | Digester A and B Feeding

The slurry was manually stirred in a different container for a short period of time before being fed to the digester. The digesters' doors were shut once the mixed waste was fed into them. Utilizing a previously published approach, it was discovered that the organic loading rate (OLR) was around 0.72 Kg of VS/m³ inside the digester. Capacity of the digester was approximately 75% filled with slurry.

2.2.3. | Data Collection and Physio-Chemical Analysis

Using a standard approach for the assessment of water and waste, the physical properties; total solids (TS), volatile solids (VS), moisture content (MC), and ash content (AC) were examined. Each digester's pH and temperature were initially assessed. At the beginning and conclusion of the digestion, samples of the slurry were taken to determine the number of TS, VS, ash, and moisture present. Temperature was monitored on the gas production volume, influent and effluent, and digester liquid pH. Efficiency of VS conversion to gas and the TS/VS loss in the fermenter were also tracked. APHA guidelines were followed in determining these criteria.

2.2.3.1. | Total Solids (TS)

Both organic and inorganic materials are represented by the feedstock's TS (Edu et al., n.d.). TS were calculated according APHA. In an empty scale (W_2), 20 g of new feedstock was weighed in a crucible (W_1) and dried for 24 hours in an oven set at 6.65 °F (W_3). Eqn. 1 was used to compute the percent TS.

$$\% = \frac{W_3 - W_1}{W_2} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

VS are the feedstock's organic materials (excluding the inorganic salts and ash). This was also assessed using APHA guidelines presented by Abubakar et al. (2022). An oven-dried sample weighing 3 g was weighed (B) in an empty crucible (A) and heated (A) to a constant weight for 1 hour in a muffle furnace (C) at 293.33°F. Specifically, Eqn. 2 was used to compute the percentage VS.

$$\%VS = \frac{C-A}{B} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

2.2.3.2. Indicator Efficiency

An indicator such as TS/VS lost was used to estimate the reactors performance and feedstock conversion efficiency. Before introducing the feedstock into the reactor, its initial TS/VS was calculated. Destructive sampling was followed by the determination of the final TS/VS. Variation between the original amount of TS/VS lost was calculated using (mass of TS/VS supplied) and final TS/VS (residual TS/VS in the digested feedstock). Eqn. 3 is used to do the calculations.

$$\left(\frac{TS}{VS}\right)_{lost} = \left(\frac{TS}{VS}\right)_{initial} - \left(\frac{TS}{VS}\right)_{final} \quad (3)$$

As previously mentioned, destructive sampling was used to determine the TS/VS lost. It was displayed in terms of liters of biogas created for each gram of TS/VS lost. This provided a process index efficiency.

2.2.3.3. Expected Gas Production Level from TS And VS Lost

To calculate the theoretical gas yield from the TS/VS loss, a mass balance method was applied. The amount of biogas generated was thought to be equal to the volume of the biogas produced. VS was lost in the procedure. Discrepancy between the actual and theoretical biogas yields resulted from physical leakage, an uneven microbe to substrate ratio, inefficient conversion processes (such as those that progress to the creation of VFA but stop short of gas), and other reasons.

3.1. | Results and Discussion

Table 2 contains the information (i.e., MC, TS, VS, and AC) on the wastes utilized for the studies.

Table 2. Characteristics of Wastes Used for Feed

S/ No	Name Of Wastes	Weight (g)	Moisture Content (%)	Total (%)	Solid (%)	Volatile Solid (%)	Ash (%)	Content	TS/VS (%)
1	Mango	7	93.1	26.4	104.8	6.2	0.37		
2	Avocado	5.4	83.2	36.8	101.24	9.76	0.49		
3	Papaya	8	88.65	31.35	102.12	8.88	0.33		
4	Tomato	7.5	93.14	26.86	102.85	8.15	0.38		
5	Banana peel	4.8	91	29	92.6	8.4	0.31		
9	Lignocellulosic waste	32.5	14.66	45.34	106.14	4.96	0.47		
10	Cow dung	13	89.75	30.25	101.56	7.44	0.32		

It is clear from Table 2 that the tomato has the highest MC, at 93.14%, while LW have the lowest moisture level, at 14.66%. Highest TS of 45.34% was discovered in LW. All of the waste utilized for the study had VS ranging from 104.8% in the mango to 106.14% in LW. The outcomes of the current study for specific wastes are equivalent to Mital's published values (Gea et al., n.d.). According to Viswanath, tomatoes and bananas each contain 11.8% and 29.5% of TS, respectively (Boukis, n.d.). These results are comparable to current values that have been recorded. And observed that the TS content in food processing wastes, such as mango, tomato, lemon, orange, and pineapple peels, ranged from 28.4% to 23.4% (Management, n.d.). The current figures for VS are likewise equivalent to the 92.73% reported in the literature for wastes from decaying fruits and vegetables. Anaerobic digestion is facilitated by the organic wastes and high MC percentage (Kougias & Angelidaki, 2018).

The following are the properties of cow dung that were examined in this paper: TS, 30.25% of wet weight, VS, 101.56%, AC, 9.44%, and MC of 89.75%. Various researches have noted various features of CM, such as 16% TS by Neves et al. (2018), 77% MC by Ye et al. (2013), 9.3% TS, and 80.3% VS by Menon et al. (2017). The values provided by these scholars are supported by the current study as well. The ratio of the comb wastes from the LW and CM was 85:25. The wastes have the following characteristics: TS, 30.65% of wet weight, VS, 10.6%, AC, 5%, and MC, 89.35%. LW combined with CM was 85:25.

These wastes have TS of 45.34% of wet weight, VS, 96.14%, AC, 4.88%, and MC of 89.35% as their main features.

In each digester, the pH of mixed wastes varied from 5.9 to 7.2, which is equivalent to the pH range that is ideal for the formation of biogas (Lindmark et al., 2014). This outcome demonstrated that the pH of the slurry in the anaerobic digesters did not have an impact on the microorganisms inside. Therefore, the pH impact has no influence on the generation of biogas from garbage combined with cow dung. All digesters had temperatures between -3.333 and 160°F, which falls within the mesophilic temperature range (-3.888 to 232.222 °F), where biogas generation is permitted.

In this study, anaerobic digesters reached their steady state 3 weeks following the start-up process. Average TS and VS reduction efficiencies for food during the steady state for LW combined with cow dung (10.96) and wastes mixed with cow dung (27.81 and 64.85, respectively). This shows that the mixed wastes turned into biogas, requires the addition of more substrate to the digester. Initial TS/VS of the mixture of cow dung and leftover fruit was 0.315. The final TS/VS of the leftover trash decreased to 0.278 after the mixed garbage underwent anaerobic digestion. The starting mass of the TS/VS residue was different by 0.137. The combined residual LW and cow dung had an initial TS/VS of 0.467. The final TS/VS of the leftover trash was 0.32 following the anaerobic digestion of the mixed garbage. The starting mass of the TS/VS residue varied by 0.147 as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Efficiency of Total Solids and Volatile Solids Reduction

Component	Fruit Waste + Cow Manure			Lignocellulosic Waste + Cow Manure		
	Initial	Final	Reduction	Initial	Final	Reduction
TS	45.34	27.53	27.81	30.65	10.96	11.69
VS	106.14	64.8	51.34	106	66	50
TS/VS	0.467	0.42	0.057	0.315	0.278	0.147

3.2. | Biogas Production

It was clear that biogas production was evident in digester A. The digesters were left for three weeks so that microorganism will generate biogas. After that, there was a pressure build-up in each digesters' empty space. Flammability of the biogas that was linked to the digester output through a rubber tube was used to evaluate the biogas produced in digesters A. Although a flame was anticipated to result from the Bunsen burner, but it was not seen. After a few days, biogas generation began in digester B. Due to lack of instruments, the complete amount of gas produced was not monitored. The recovered biogas from digester A is expressed as 0.057 l/g (57 mL/g), which is the ratio of TS/VS lost from fruits combined with cow dung. The biogas generated from cow manure and fruit contains 0.047 l/g (47 mL/g). Biogas that was produced by water displacement method from residual fruits combined with cow dung is 0.052 l/g (52 mL/g). LW wastes combined with cow dung yield 0.041 l/g (31 mL/g) of biogas.

The variation in biogas evaluated by the TS/VS ratio and displacement technique indicates distinct types of gas leakage. According to measured results, fruits combined with cow dung would produce more biogas than LW combined with cow manure. The biogas produced in 'A' may not burn when ignited because of insufficient microorganism in the substrate to produce CH₄ from acetic acid and carbon dioxide which may result in the build-up of digested particles at the digester's bottom. Also causing scum to appear on the slurry's surface. Contact between the microorganisms and the substrates is not sufficient and the environment's temperature was lower (out of the mesophilic range) during the construction of the digester. As a result, the gas production will start to decline and eventually stop.

4.0. | Conclusion

After 21 days, biogas was produced in both digesters. According to measured results, fruits combined with cow dung would produce more biogas than LW waste combined with cow manure. Lowering of TS/VS shows that more biogas will be produced from leftover fruits combined with cow dung. Temperature, pH, volatile fatty acids, microbial population, and ammonia all have an impact on the microbial

nature of the biogas generation process. The quantity and quality of biogas generated depends on how well these variables controlled. The slurry which comes out of the over flow pipe which is fixed in the middle of the drum shown in Fig. 2 can be used as liquid fertilizer which tends to boost plant growth. The creation of biogas from fruits waste is a significant step toward achieving a renewable energy source in the world, especially in the generation of electricity.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest exists in the course of writing this work. All parties agree to the content of the work.

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